

EDUCATION MANAGEMENT

Matyakubova F.B.

Major, Instructor at the Institute for Advanced Training of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14280866>

Abstract. *This article will discuss the topic of education management and its current trends that are going on. The article will provide with pioneers and their works to give insight how it evolved and concepts that are available now.*

Keywords: *SEL, LMS, adaptability, green education, curricula, analytics in education, predictive analytics in education.*

INTRODUCTION

Education management refers to the process of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling educational institutions and systems. It involves various activities aimed at improving the quality of education and ensuring that educational goals are met effectively and efficiently. There are some steps that education management is carried out. Strategic planning is developing long-term goals and objectives for educational institutions and assessing resources and needs to implement effective educational programs.

Another key aspect is operational management, which is overseeing the daily operations of schools or educational organizations and managing staff, resources, and facilities to ensure a conducive learning environment, as well. Moreover, recruiting, training, and evaluating teachers and administrative staff is human resource management and it is also ensuring professional development opportunities for educators. Education management also involves curriculum development, which means designing and implementing curricula that meet educational standards and student needs. It is also evaluating and updating educational programs based on feedback and academic performance.

Evaluation and assessment are another part of education management as a key point. It deals with monitoring and assessing the effectiveness of educational programs and initiatives and using data to inform decision-making and improve educational outcomes.

Education management plays a crucial role in shaping the educational landscape, ensuring that institutions function smoothly and that students receive a quality education. Effective management contributes to the overall success of educational systems and the development of future generations.

Current trends in education management reflect the evolving needs of students, educators, and the broader society. The following paragraphs will explore some these trends that will illustrate the evolution and modern trends.

Initial ongoing trend is digital transformation. The rise of online and blended learning models, especially accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, has changed how education is delivered. It increased use of LMS platforms to facilitate course delivery, track progress, and enhance student engagement.

Another trend is focus on social-emotional learning (SEL). It means holistic education to some extent. Growing recognition of the importance of students' emotional and social well-being

alongside academic achievement. It ensures implementation of curricula and programs that support emotional intelligence, resilience, and interpersonal skills.

Another trend is analytics in education. It means increasing reliance on data analytics to assess student performance, inform instructional practices, and improve educational outcomes. There is also predictive analytics, which involves using data to anticipate student needs and identify at-risk learners for timely intervention.

Apart from these trends, there are some society-related ones such as collaborative learning environments. One form of it is team-based learning, which encourages collaboration among students through group projects and peer-to-peer learning. Another one is community partnerships, which builds connections with local organizations and businesses to enhance educational opportunities and resources.

Education management also involves current social and environmental factors. It gives an emergence of Green Education Initiatives. This incorporates sustainability into curricula and promoting environmentally responsible practices within educational institutions. Moreover, there is equity and inclusion, on the other hand. It means efforts to create more inclusive educational environments that address disparities in access and outcomes.

These trends in education management reflect a shift towards more flexible, responsive, and inclusive educational practices. By embracing these trends, educational institutions can better prepare students for the challenges of the modern world and foster a more equitable and effective learning environment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The contribution was done by several pioneers who developed one concept or model in this sphere. One of them is Peter Senge, who advocates for the concept of the "learning organization," where continuous learning and adaptive leadership are essential for educational institutions. His notable work is "The Fifth Discipline: The Art & Practice of The Learning Organization", (1990). Michael Fullan focuses on educational change and the importance of leadership in fostering improvement within schools. His work titled "Leading in a Culture of Change" (2001) is popular for contributing education management.

Another scholar is John Hattie who emphasizes the significance of evidence-based practices in education, advocating for strategies that have a measurable impact on student learning by his work of "Visible Learning: A Synthesis of Over 800 Meta-Analyses Relating to Achievement" (2009). The importance of teacher quality and professional development in improving educational outcomes was highlighted by Linda Darling-Hammond in the work "The Right to Learn: A Blueprint for Creating Schools That Work" (1997).

Henry Mintzberg - although primarily known for his work in management, Mintzberg's ideas on organizational structure and management styles have influenced educational leadership practices. His contributory work is titled as "The Rise and Fall of Strategic Planning" (1994).

Another scholar is Carol Dweck who known for her research on mindset. He emphasizes the importance of fostering a growth mindset in students and educators to enhance learning and resilience, whose work "Mindset: The New Psychology of Success" is so prominent.

These scholars contribute valuable perspectives to the field of education management, emphasizing the importance of leadership, evidence-based practices, and continuous improvement. Their works provide frameworks and strategies for enhancing educational effectiveness and fostering a culture of learning within institutions.

There are several reasons why education management is essential. The first one is effective resource utilization. It ensures that financial, human, and physical resources are allocated efficiently to enhance educational outcomes.

Another reason is quality improvement. Through strategic planning and implementation of best practices, education management promotes continuous improvement in teaching and learning. Moreover, it ensures adaptability to change. It helps educational institutions respond to changes in technology, curriculum, and societal needs, ensuring relevance and effectiveness.

On the other hand, it guarantees leadership and governance. Strong education management provides clear leadership and governance, fostering a positive organizational culture and enhancing stakeholder engagement.

CONCLUSION

In summary, effective education management is crucial for optimizing resources, improving quality, adapting to changes, providing leadership, and making informed decisions, all of which contribute to the success of educational institutions.

REFERENCES

1. Dr. Ruth Colvin Clark- Building Expertise: Cognitive Methods for Training and Performance Improvement (2008, San Francisco, CA: Pfeiffer).
2. Dr. Tony Bates - Teaching in a Digital Age: Guidelines for Designing Teaching and Learning (2015, Vancouver, BC: Tony Bates Associates Ltd).
3. Dr. Allen Tough - The Adult Learning Project: A Comprehensive Guide to the Theory and Practice of Adult Learning (1971, Toronto, ON: Ontario Institute for Studies in Education).
4. Dr. Jay Cross - Informal Learning: Rediscovering the Natural Pathways That Inspire Innovation and Performance (2007, San Francisco, CA: Pfeiffer).
5. Dr. Jennifer Hofmann - The Blended Learning Book: Best Practices, Proven Methodologies, and Lessons Learned (2010, Hoboken, NJ: Wiley).
6. Жураев Б. Т. Гуманизация дидактических отношений между учителем и учащимся в педагогических идеях Востока //VIII Лазаревские чтения" Лики традиционной культуры в современном культурном пространстве: ренессанс базовых ценностей?". – 2018. – С. 120-122.
7. Жураев Б. Т. Деятельность педагога по гуманизации учебновоспитательного процесса //Научные школы. Молодежь в науке и культуре XXI в.: материалы междунар. науч.-творч. форума. – 2017. – Т. 31.
8. Жураев Б. Т. Некоторые вопросы наставничества в педагогическом наследии Хусаина Воиза Кошифи //Социально-культурная деятельность: векторы исследовательских и практических перспектив. – 2016. – С. 103-105.
9. Dr. Harold Jarche - PKM in 40 Days (2013, Available online).
10. Dr. Charles Jennings - The 70:20:10 Framework: The Future of Learning and Development (2016, London, UK: Learning and Performance Institute).